

INNOVATIVE APPROACHES TO THE ACTIVITIES OF THE EDUCATOR OF THE PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10643047>

Annotation: this article quotes new innovative methods and approaches to the interaction of educators and parents in relation to preschool education organization and family cooperation, including technologies to facilitate communication and cooperation. Various studies and theories related to the activities of the educator and innovative approaches related to cooperation with the family are also presented in the context of preschool organizations. They include development theories, examples of specific pedagogical approaches, and proposals for practical cooperation between parents, caregivers, and the public.

Keywords: preschool education, innovative approach, project activities, master classes, individual approach, dynamism

The participation of parents in preschool educational organizations leads to an excellent result both for upbringing and for children. The role of the family in the upbringing of a child is incomparable. The family has a strong influence on the child, adapting him to the life around him. And in society, upbringing is not only the personal work of the parents, but also their social duty. Involving parents in organizational work such as making a soft toy, making toys to play with water and sand, and preparing equipment to Green the grounds are important activities. Such choices must be reflected in the educator's annual work plan. The terms of the competition must be discussed and approved at General parent meetings. To declare gratitude to active participating parents, it is necessary to listen to the advice of both grandparents and grandfathers in this regard.

It can be very difficult to establish cooperation with families whose opinions differ from ours or with a family that does not participate in different activities as expected by educators. We can even believe that these families care less about their children and their education, or that they have relatively little knowledge in raising their own children.

Let's consider innovative methods of working with the family, ways to develop cooperation between the preschool organization and parents:

Project activities: involve parents in the development and implementation of projects aimed at developing children and improving their educational and educational conditions.

Master classes: the organization of master classes for parents, where teachers share their experiences and give practical recommendations on various aspects of the upbringing and development of children.

Parent meetings in interactive form: the use of interactive methods and technologies such as Game techniques, discussions, roundtables, etc. to discuss issues related to the educational process and cooperation with the family.

Organization of family holidays and events: organization of joint celebrations and events that promote cooperation between the family and teachers, as well as the development of children.

The creation of remote forms of communication: the use of modern information technologies for the exchange of information and experience between teachers and parents, as well as for conducting consultations and seminars.

The partnership requires respect for the other party, responding to their needs, and expressing their own reaction to what works and what doesn't. To start such a relationship, educators need to know information about the family of the children they raise. The family is the first and most important educator of children.

It is very important to recognize and appreciate the main role of the family as the first educator of the child. Parents and other close family members are the most important people in the life of a small child, becoming their first and longest teachers. In the family environment, the following sensations are formed in children:

- the sense of belonging and communication with the community in which they live;
- physical well-being, including food, shelter, clothing and medical services;
- flourishing development, including their emotional, social, spiritual, linguistic and physical development, a sense of identity as a member of family, culture and society.

At the beginning of preschool education, families would have taught children most skills: from eating and drinking to looking after themselves and others. Most of them help children learn how to meet their needs, how to behave according to their age and culture, as well as how to communicate verbally and non-verbally in their native language.

The role of an educator in the cooperation of families and the local community is incomparable. The competent upbringing of children cannot be achieved without the active participation of their parents and the public in the educational process, since the parents' views on the cooperation of the PRESCHOOL with the family differ, the aspects of parental satisfaction from the conditions of the PRESCHOOL are changing, and this causes the following problems:

first, in some families, the tendency of parents to give up on solving issues of raising and personal development of their children has increased;

secondly, some parents, on the other hand, are interested only in the nutrition of the child, they consider PRESCHOOL to be a place where only children are fed;

third, it is believed that the PRESCHOOL should educate their children;

fourth, there is also a category of parents who ignore the advice of caregivers. Some parents believe that their task is to ensure that only the child is dressed.

The involvement of parents in the field of pedagogical activity, their interest in the process of educational gaming activity is very important for their child.

So, how can the educator contribute to the greater involvement and activity of parents in the process of educational gaming activities?

The high-quality education of our children, the full satisfaction of the needs of parents and the interests of children, the creation of a single educational space for a child can be achieved only from early childhood, when we developed a new system of mutual cooperation between guardianship and family.

The influence of family and young child care on the development of the personality of preschool children is carried out in principle through the joint activities of educators,

community organizations and families, in which all individuals, organizations, community organizations engaged in upbringing must act together, show agreed requirements to each other, help each other, complement and strengthen pedagogical influence. If such solidarity and coordination of efforts is not achieved, then it is difficult to achieve success.

The organization of family and community interaction with PRESCHOOL is based on the following basic principles:

1. Friendly communication between educators and parents

This principle expresses a positive attitude to communication and is based on all the work of early childhood education educators with parents.

Educators communicate with parents every day, and this depends on what the attitude of the whole family towards preschool education will be. Daily benevolent communication between caregivers and parents means more than a separate event.

This principle implies a positive attitude to communication and provides a basis for educators to work with parents throughout their career. In the communication of educators with the categories of parents, a demanding tone is not suitable.

2. Individual approach

This principle of cooperation is important not only in working with children, but also in working with parents. Caregivers who interact with parents should feel the situation, the mood of the parents. The importance here lies in the caregivers' belief in parents, empathy, and the ability and pedagogical ability to think together about how they can help a child in a particular situation.

3. Cooperation, not coaching

Most modern mothers and fathers are educated, educated and, of course, well know how to raise their own children. Therefore, today the position of teaching and simple promotion of pedagogical knowledge cannot lead to positive results. In difficult pedagogical situations, it is necessary to recognize that the PRESCHOOL team wants to sincerely help in solving family problems in creating an atmosphere of mutual support and support for the family, understanding and finding a solution to family problems.

4. Dynamism

PRESCHOOL today should be in a development mode, not a simple mode of Operation, be a mobile system, quickly meet the changes in the social structure of parents, their educational needs and requirements for education. It follows from this that the form and directions of work of the PRESCHOOL with the family must change.

5. Openness

The openness of a preschool organization to the family is to provide each parent with the opportunity to know and see how their child lives and develops. This is important in preventing the emergence of problematic situations, it is necessary to establish personal ties between educators and parents, to inform parents every day about how the child spent the day, what he learned, what achievements he achieved. On the basis of this, the support of the psychological abilities of parents has become the most relevant task of the modern era.

The joint activities of parents and caregivers allow us to jointly identify and solve their existing problems in raising children. Such cooperation will help in the following aspects:

- exploring opportunities for education on both sides;
- joint identification of achievements and problems with the Educator (of the child

based on development map data);

- joint project activities of children and adults in terms of actual problems of teaching, education and development.

Based on the collaborative approach above, PRESCHOOL's together with families and the local community define the goals and objectives of the PRESCHOOL.

Goals:

For interaction with parents and the local community
creating a comfortable environment.

Establish interaction with parents and the local community.

Activation of the participation of parents in the educational process, in various additional activities.

Assignments:

To establish cooperation with parents and support their psychological and pedagogical skills.

Establishing game partnerships with children and helping them develop successfully in preschool educational organizations.

The family is an institution for raising children. Therefore, it is necessary to carefully react to state-level reformist changes in the structure of society, as long as their results are directly reflected in the level of family life, stability and educational disadvantage.

The culture of human education has discovered two effective institutions – PRESCHOOL and family. The family forms actions that do not go to the level of heredity. The family is such a place in which, in terms of importance, specific norms of movement in society are formed for the next generation, which are not inferior to the educational institution[1].

Azimov A. In a study, the author examines the pedagogical conditions of cooperation between the family and preschool institutions in the context of preparing children for school. This study considers the main competencies of the educator, such as participation, communication and cooperation[2].

F.U. Mirzayev and G.S. The ahmedovas discuss the professional development of preschool educators, focusing on the problems and prospects of cooperation with families. They emphasize the importance for caregivers to develop basic competencies to communicate effectively with parents and involve them in the learning process[3].

Modern research in this area often focuses on developing new innovative methods and approaches to the interaction of educators and parents, including the use of technology to facilitate communication and collaboration. These resources provide a variety of studies and theories related to educator activities and innovative approaches related to family cooperation in the context of preschool organizations. They include development theories, examples of specific pedagogical approaches, and proposals for practical cooperation between parents, teachers, and the public.

Is the study of an innovative approach to education in Redjio Emilia, Italy[4]. Redjio Emilia is a pedagogical approach based on the principles of active participation of children, parents and teachers in the educational process[5]. In this study, the authors analyze the relationship between family and educator collaboration and children's success in the academic and social field.

S. M. Sheridan, T. R. In the work of the kratochwills, the authors propose an approach that helps to develop interactions between family and caregivers and discuss the competencies necessary to successfully implement this approach[6].

A. T. Henderson, CA. L. In their scientific research, Mapps, on the other hand, study the impact of family and educator interaction on student success, emphasizing the importance of basic teacher competencies for effective collaboration[7].

Evaluates the importance and key factors of parent participation in preschool programs and the role of educators and class characteristics in the process. Basic competencies of caregivers for successful collaboration with families in preschool education can include the following skills and knowledge. (See table 1.1.1)

1.1.1-table

Types of operation	Relationships
Contact	teachers should be good listeners and be able to express their thoughts clearly and correctly. They must maintain open and honest communication with parents, taking into account various cultural and social contexts.
Collaboration	educators should be prepared to work together with parents and other family members, participate in the Joint Planning and evaluation of educational activities, and develop cooperation.
Feeling and sensitivity	educators should be sensitive to the needs and feelings of the family, strive to understand their point of view, and be willing to support and help when necessary.
Knowing the development of the child	teachers should be deeply aware of the features of the physical, intellectual, social and emotional development of preschool children. This helps them to better explain to the parents the dynamics of their child's development and offer appropriate support strategies.
Flexibility and adaptability	educators must be prepared to adapt to different situations, family structures and cultural characteristics and be able to find individual approaches to families, taking into account their needs and capabilities.
Professional development	educators must constantly improve their knowledge and skills, monitor new trends and research in preschool education and family cooperation, and put this knowledge into practice.
The ability to involve the family in the educational process	educators should look for different ways in which the family actively participates in the life of a preschool institution, offer interesting forms of interaction and encourage family education.
Respect for diversity	educators must respect the different cultural, religious and social characteristics of families, given their values and views on the upbringing and education of children.
Reflection	educators must constantly analyze and evaluate their activities in the context of cooperation with families, find opportunities for improvement and apply the knowledge they have acquired to optimize their relationships.

Conflict agement	educators should be prepared to prevent and resolve possible conflicts with parents, to find compromises and agreements that will satisfy the interests of all parties.
Use of technology	educators should be familiar with modern technologies and use them to improve interaction with families, exchange information and learn.
Organization of its and projects	educators must be able to develop and organize various activities and projects that involve families in the educational process and help strengthen cooperation between the family and the preschool institution.

The development of these basic competencies in educators will help them successfully cooperate with families in preschool institutions and create conditions for the harmonious development of children. The interaction of PRESCHOOL and parents allows to increase the quality and efficiency of the educational process, develop the creative potential of children and strengthen cooperation between family and educators. However, for the successful application of these methods, it is necessary to actively support the administration of educational organizations, as well as to constantly improve the qualifications of educators and develop professional competencies.

Thus, relying on the scientific analyzes we have carried out, we propose the following innovative ways to work with the family:

Project activities: involve parents in the development and implementation of projects aimed at developing children and improving their educational and educational conditions.

Master classes: Organization of master classes for parents, where educators share their experiences and give practical recommendations on various aspects of raising and developing children.

Parents ' meetings in interactive form: the use of interactive methods and technologies such as Game techniques, discussions, roundtables, etc.to discuss issues related to the learning process and cooperation with the family.

Organization of family holidays and events: the organization of joint celebrations and events that promote cooperation between family and caregivers, as well as the development of children.

Creating remote forms of communication: the use of modern information technology to exchange information and experience between educators and parents, as well as to conduct consultations and seminars.

In conclusion, in preschool educational organizations, the successful application of innovative methods of working with the caregiver family helps to strengthen interaction between caregivers and the family, create a favorable psychological environment and effectively develop children. An important aspect of the successful use of innovative methods is flexibility and individual approach to each family, taking into account the interests and developmental characteristics of children, as well as encouraging and supporting educators in their pursuit of continuous professional growth and development. In conclusion, innovative methods of working with the family are an integral part of modern preschool education. It allows you to improve the quality and efficiency of the educational process, develop the creative potential of

children and strengthen cooperation between the family and the tarbmacists. However, for the successful application of these methods, it is necessary to actively support the administration of educational organizations, as well as to constantly improve the qualifications of educators and develop professional competencies.

References:

- 1.Tulenov J. Qadriyatlar falsafasi. – T.: O‘zbekiston, 1998. – 335 b.
- 2.Azimov, A.A. Bolalarning maktabda o‘qishga tayyorligini shakllantirishda oila va maktabgacha ta’lim muassasasi o‘rtasidagi hamkorlikning pedagogik shartlari. Pedagogika fanlari nomzodi ilmiy darajasini olishga dissertatsiya. Toshkent shahri. (2015).
- 3.Mirzayev, F.U. va Ahmedova, G.S. (2019). Maktabgacha ta’lim pedagoglarining kasbiy rivojlanishi: muammolar va istiqbollar. Pedagogik innovatsiyalar axborotnomasi, 1(1), 5-12.
- 4.Edwards, C., Gandini, L., & Forman, G. (Eds.). (2012). Sotrudnichestvo mejdu roditelyami i pedagogami v Redjio-Emiliya: Protsess otkrytiya sebya i drugix. Teachers College Press.
- 5.Powell, D. R., Son, S.-H., File, N., & San Juan, R. R. (2010). Parent–school relationships and children’s academic and social outcomes in public pre-kindergarten. *Journal of School Psychology*, 48(4), 269–292.
- 6.Sheridan, S. M., & Kratochwill, T. R. (2007). *Conjoint Behavioral Consultation: Promoting Family-School Connections and Interventions*. Springer Science & Business Media.
- 7.Henderson, A. T., & Mapp, K. L. (2002). *A New Wave of Evidence: The Impact of School, Family, and Community Connections on Student Achievement*. National Center for Family & Community Connections with Schools.